

THE ROLE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO TEACH VOCABULARY TO LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Murodillayev Behzod

The Student of Doctor of Philosophy of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10349363>

Abstract

This paper is aimed to acknowledge and study the importance of usage of mobile applications and platforms while teaching a language, especially vocabulary aspect of the language. It discusses the role and benefits of this quite novel approach to teaching vocabulary as well as shed light on a few applications that have been used in teaching vocabulary in language classes.

Introduction

Language learning methods have been developing considerably throughout the period of technological advancements. Emerging technologies have significantly transformed how teaching and learning are conducted. Mobile phones, in particular, have sparked numerous research studies on their educational applications, impacting language teaching practices as well. Mobile learning has revolutionized traditional teaching methods by offering adaptable, convenient, and customized learning experiences both in and outside the classroom.

The focus on vocabulary is integral to attaining proficiency and competence in a second language. Persistent efforts have been made to find effective methods for teaching vocabulary, as it is fundamental to language learning. Idiomatic expressions, in particular, are commonly used non-literal phrases and serve as key components in everyday conversations. Therefore, a deficiency in using them proficiently can lead to communication issues for language learners, resulting in unnatural and inauthentic dialogue.

English instructors need to employ diverse methods to instruct vocabulary, as it is a crucial aspect of language mastery. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are the primary skills that students must excel in. However, to effectively practice these skills, students need a robust vocabulary. Shen (2003) has acknowledged that effective communication is challenging without a strong vocabulary. Therefore, it is imperative for ESL teachers to integrate vocabulary instruction while teaching listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, given the interconnected nature of these skills.

Literature review

Although, the use of mobile applications in teaching vocabulary is quite a novel method, many researchers and ESL teachers have been researching on its efficacy through various researches and teaching procedures. Multiple experimental studies examined the effectiveness of vocabulary instruction through SMS messages in comparison to various traditional instructional methods. For instance, Lu (2008) and Zhang et al. (2011) sought to assess the impact of SMS messages versus printed materials.

Moreover, Basoglu and Akdemir (2010) undertook research on vocabulary acquisition, comparing the use of mobile phones and flashcards. The experimental group used a mobile application to learn words over six weeks, while the control group learned the same words using flashcards.

Lawrence (2014) utilized WhatsApp groups to teach vocabulary to a group of undergraduate learners of Afrikaans, introducing new words before reading texts. Over a 7-week period, the researchers sent messages to the group containing translations and various media, including sound or images, to introduce target words.

Also, other skilled and successful researchers have carried out researches on the usage and development of mobile applications in teaching vocabulary to language learners.

Methodology

For the use of applications in teaching, a wide range of approaches can be implemented in the lessons. First of all, illustrations are of the utmost importance and effectiveness as they are easier to attract the students. Many researchers have used different methods to teach vocabulary through mobile platforms and applications.

Castrillo et al. (2014) studied how WhatsApp facilitated the negotiation of meaning among 85 Spanish learners of German. The students were divided into 5 WhatsApp groups and were given topics to discuss. The researchers analyzed the students' interactions, their ability to negotiate meaning, and their engagement with the tasks. The study found that the students displayed high motivation and participation, and had improved their skills in negotiating meaning.

Krashen (1985) formulated The Affective Filter Hypothesis which proposes that learners have a mental block, known as the affective filter, that can regulate the access to comprehensible input needed for language acquisition. His theory focuses on how the affective filter of learners can influence the intake of new input. He suggested that individuals acquire second languages when they

receive comprehensible input and their affective filters are sufficiently low to permit the input.

Research and Result

The current study's results about the impact of the WhatsApp application are consistent with Stockwell's (2007) findings, indicating that the use of mobile applications had a significant effect on learners' vocabulary knowledge. Similarly, the outcome aligns with the conclusions of Thornton and Houser, who observed a positive reception of educational materials for mobile phones in language learning and recognized the platform as effective for vocabulary acquisition.

Thornton and Houser (2005) conducted a study on the application of mobile devices in language learning. The findings indicated that students responded favorably to educational materials tailored for mobile phones, and they were able to engage in effective learning through this method. The researchers also noted that mobile phones served as highly effective tools for vocabulary acquisition, as they captured the students' attention and provided new learning prospects.

Therefore, various scholars (Anderson, 2001; Lowe, Mayfield, & Reynolds, 2003) highlight the superiority of females in verbal and language tasks compared to males. In a similar vein, Salamat and Pourgharib (2013) conducted a study aiming to enhance the speaking skills of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students through mobile phone usage. The study involved 40 participants, both male and female, within the 18-25 age range. Results indicated that individuals who utilized mobile-assisted learning showed significantly greater improvement in speaking ability compared to those in the control group.

Discussion

Comparing the scores of students on a vocabulary pre-test and post-test revealed that the use of WhatsApp had a significant impact on their vocabulary knowledge. These results align with a study by Gooniband Shooshtari, Jalilifar & Khazaie (2013) that looked at the influence of mobile devices on teaching English vocabulary, which also found success in improving vocabulary retention. Additionally, the findings of this study are consistent with Baolu's (2010) research, which showed that participants who used a mobile application had better word recall compared to those who used traditional methods. The current study's results also support Stickler and Hampel's (2010) findings that online language courses can incorporate various learning and teaching approaches, such as communicative language use and language practice. Moreover, they are

in line with Taki and Khazaei's (2011) study on the use of mobile phones to present vocabulary in written and pictorial formats.

Suwantarathip and Orawiwatnakul (2015) discovered that the group using mobile-assisted vocabulary exercises performed better than the control group using paper-based exercises. These findings are in line with the results of our current research, which also supports the notion that using mobile applications is more effective for teaching vocabulary than traditional methods.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the role of mobile applications and platforms is getting more and more prominent and promising in teaching vocabulary to young learners as they are sophisticated and futuristic. Furthermore, as many people spend greater amount of time on mobile phones, this method gives opportunities to teach them with the way they prefer more. As a result, language learning process can be not only more straightforward but also more efficacious through those applications.

References:

1. Anderson, J. (2001). Net effect of memory collaboration: How is collaboration affected by factors such as friendship, gender, and age? *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 42, 367-375. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1467-9450.00248>
2. Basoglu, E. B. & Akdemir, O. (2010). A comparison of undergraduate students' English vocabulary learning: Using mobile phones and flash cards. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 9(3), 1-7
3. Castrillo(2014). Mobile--based chatting for meaning negotiation in foreign language learning. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Mobile Learning*. International Association for Development of the Information Society (pp. 49-59)
4. Grant, L. E. (2007). In a manner of speaking: Assessing frequent spoken figurative idioms to assist ESL/EFL teachers. *System*, 35(2), 169-181
5. Lawrence, D. (2014) Students' experiences of using SMS for Vocabulary Development. Case Study. In *Conference proceedings of ICT for language learning* (p. 310). Available at: <http://www.libreriauniversitaria>
6. Lu, M. (2008). Effectiveness of vocabulary learning via mobile phone. *Journal of computer assisted learning*, 24(6), 515-525
7. Stockwell, G. (2007). A review of technology choice for teaching language skills and areas in the CALL literature. *ReCALL*, 19(2), 105-120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0958344007000225>
8. Thornton, P., & Houser, C. (2005). Using mobile phones in English education in Japan. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 21, 217-228. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2005.00129.x>

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

9. Wong, K. C., Lam, Y. R., & Ho, L. M. (2002). The effect of schooling on gender differences. *British Educational Research Journal*, 28, 827-843.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0141192022000019080>